

FUCE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN RELATION TO THEIR LICENSURE EXAMINATION RATING

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the undergraduate academic performance of teacher education students and their Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results. The study included 58 randomly selected graduates: 27 from Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) and 31 from Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) from 2017 to 2021. Data mining was used to gather information on students' academic performance in General Education, Professional Education, and specialization subjects, along with their LET ratings. A descriptive-correlation method was employed to analyze the data. The results showed that BSEd graduates had academic performance ratings of Superior, Very Good, and Good in their Major, Professional Education, and General Education subjects, respectively. Their LET performance was average, with a strong correlation between General Education grades and LET results, but weaker correlations in Professional and Specialization subjects. BEEd graduates had Very Good academic performance but below-average LET results. The study found a moderate correlation between BEEd students' LET performance and their grades in Professional Education subjects, and a very weak correlation with General Education subjects.

Keywords: *LET Performance, Undergraduates' Academic Performance, Specialization subjects, General Education, Professional Education*

INTRODUCTION

“Foundation University College of Education (FUCE) is the home of competent future teachers and lifelong learners where creative ideas are generated, positive work values honed and respect for individuality embraced.” This vision is the guiding post by every mentor of the college to bethink of one’s critical role in producing competent graduates who will become future teachers and contribute to the attainment of excellence in education.

Cognizant of the very important role of teachers in nation building, RA 7836 known as the Teacher Professionalization Act of 1994 was promulgated. This is to promote the development and professionalization of teachers, supervise and regulate the Licensure Examination for Teachers administered by the Philippine Regulatory Commission (PRC).

The Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) which was formerly known as the Philippine Board Examination for Teachers (PBET) is meant to find out the extent of the knowledge gained by the graduates of Teacher Education Institutions. The LET serves as an essential benchmark for ensuring the quality of teacher education, as it assesses the minimum competencies required for professional practice. In 2017, the Department of Education through the Teacher Education Council (TEC) adopted and implemented the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) through the issuance of DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017. The PPST becomes a mechanism for teachers to acknowledge the significance of the professional standards in instituting continuing professional development for all of them as lifelong learners. It is through the results of the LET that only those who have shown hard work, mastery and competence of the craft are capable of entering into the teaching profession.

Accrediting bodies of Teacher Education Institutions look into the performance of the graduates in the LET as one of the barometers to measure the effectiveness of the program offerings. The LET performance can be an affirmation of how good a TEI is, in producing graduates by aligning all course requirements to the course outcomes based on the legal mandates stipulated in the CHED Memorandum Orders. It is then of importance that teacher education institutions must align their instructional delivery with LET competencies to improve outcomes.

This has propelled FUCE as a TEI to produce graduates who eventually will pass the Licensure Examination as it is committed to live by the University’s life purpose which is “to educate and develop individuals to become productive, creative, useful and responsible citizens of society.

Since 2017, performance of FUCE graduates in the LET has been consistently above the National Passing Percentage for both the Bachelor of Elementary Education and the Bachelor of Secondary of Education graduates except in September of 2017, where the college registered only 21.43% as against the National Passing Percentage which was 26.33.

Several studies had been conducted by different TEIs with the intention to improve the performance of their graduates in the LET. They further disclosed that students' academic performance showed high and slightly moderate correlation in the general education, professional education and specialization subjects. These findings, led them to conclude that students' academic performance is a significant predictor in their LET performances. In the study of Ventayen (2020), Gaviola (2019), and Amanonce (2020), they discovered that students' academic performance has a significant relationship with LET performance. Gaviola added that Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education graduates performed best in the professional Education Component, while the BSEd graduates exhibited poorest performance in the General education component of the LET.

Moreover, Apare and Arcilla (2018) also divulged that the students' academic achievement in their undergraduate subjects had a positive and significant relationship to their performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. They established that their undergraduate preparations significantly contribute to their performance in the LET. The study conducted by Quiambao, et al. (2015) also revealed that the educational attainment of teachers, the length of service, quality of library and laboratory facilities including the Grade Point Average (GPA) and the intelligent quotient of the students are very critical predictors for passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers. Faltado (2014) also pointed out that the effective delivery of curriculum and instruction is a significant predictor of passing the LET. Kalaw (2019) also emphasized the importance of enhancing faculty competence to provide students with appropriate training and quality education. Hence, it is by and large that perhaps all these factors shall also be highly considered by FUCE in developing interventions, innovations and initiatives for better LET performance of its graduates especially so, that no similar research was conducted before.

Given these contexts, the researchers looked into the LET performance of the Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education graduates of FUCE within the AY 2017-2021. The intention of this endeavor is established baseline statistics for data-driven interventions to institutionalize practices and processes towards strengthening instructional practices of General Education, Professional Education and Specialization subjects. The results of the study will also dictate the direction of the FUCE in improving its facilities, laboratories and other resources contributory to achieving the desire to further improve the LET performance of its graduates.

Research Questions

This study is designed to determine Foundation University College of Education Students Academic performance and its relationship to their LET results.

Specifically, the study would like to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' performance in the following undergraduate courses:

- 1.1 General Education;

- 1.2 Professional Education; and
 - 1.3 Major subjects?
2. What is the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' performance in the Licensure Examination in the following courses:
 - 2.1 General Education;
 - 2.2 Professional Education; and
 - 2.3 Major subjects?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' performance in their undergraduate courses and their Licensure Examination results?
 4. What is the Bachelor of Elementary Education Students' performance in the following undergraduate courses:
 - 4.1 General Education; and
 - 4.2 Professional Education subjects?
5. What is the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' performance in the Licensure Examination in the following courses:
 - 5.1 General Education; and
 - 5.2 Professional Education subjects?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the Bachelor of Elementary Education Students' performance in their undergraduate courses and their Licensure Examination results?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The nature of the research is descriptive- correlational because it intends to describe the student teachers' performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers and determine whether such performance is affected by the student teachers' general education, professional education and major subjects' academic performance.

Research Environment

The study considered the College of Education graduates of Foundation University, a non-sectarian, and a non-profit university. College of Education is a level 3 accredited program of Foundation University recognized by the Philippine Association of Colleges and Universities Commission on Accreditation.

Research Participants

The respondents of the study are the graduates of Foundation University College of Education from Academic Year 2017-2020 who took and passed the LET. The respondents were randomly selected using the fish-bowl method.

Research Instrument

In this study, data mining was utilized as a strategy in gathering the respondents' LET performance and their academic performance in the general education, professional education and major subjects.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers had to follow certain protocols during the gathering of data. First, they sought permission from the students who were identified as the respondents of the study to access their grades in the online evaluation and asked their cooperation to answer the Google forms for their ratings in areas such as: General education; Professional education; and major subjects. Majority of our respondents were not hesitant to share their ratings and in fact they sent a picture of their LET results.

Data collection began after the confirmation of consents from our respondents. The researchers using the MS-excel entered the respondents' grades per subject classified under clusters such as: general education; professional education and major subjects. The same application was also used in tallying the data of the respondents' LET ratings. The data collected were treated using the different statistical tools such as mean in getting the average rating of BSEd and BEEd students' academic performance in their General education; Professional education and Major subjects. Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient was also utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the BSEd and BEEd students' academic performance and their LET ratings.

RESULTS

Table 1
BSEd Students' Performance in Undergraduate Courses (N = 27)

Courses	Rating	sd	Verbal Description
General Education Subjects	89.39	3.38	Good
Professional Education Subjects	91.45	2.84	Very Good
Major Subjects	92.74	2.73	Superior
Average	91.19	2.47	Very Good

Legend: Rating	Verbal Description
99% - 100%	Exceptional
96% - 98%	Excellent
93% - 95%	Superior
90% - 92%	Very Good
87% - 89%	Good
84% - 86%	Above Average
81% - 83%	Average
78% - 80%	Below Average
75% - 77%	Passing

Table 2
BSEd Students' Performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (N = 27)

Courses	Rating	sd	Verbal Description
General Education Subjects	82.78	4.78	Average
Professional Education Subjects	80.78	3.74	Average
Major Subjects	79.96	4.16	Below Average
Average	81.17	3.40	Average

Legend: Rating	Verbal Description
99% - 100%	Exceptional
96% - 98%	Excellent
93% - 95%	Superior
90% - 92%	Very Good
87% - 89%	Good
84% - 86%	Above Average
81% - 83%	Average
78% - 80%	Below Average
75% - 77%	Passing

Table 3
Relationship between BSEd Students' Performance in Their Undergraduate Courses and Their Licensure Examination for Teachers (N = 27)

Undergraduate Courses	Licensure Examination for Teachers			
	General Subjects	Ed. Professional Ed. Subjects	Major Subjects	Average
General Ed. Subjects	0.623 (strong)	0.534 (strong)	0.413 (moderate)	0.643 (strong)
Professional Ed Subjects	0.146 (weak)	0.110 (weak)	0.145 (weak)	0.163 (weak)
Major Subjects	0.018 (very weak)	-0.260 (weak)	0.166 (weak)	-0.030 (very weak)
Average	0.352	0.186	0.313	0.346

(moderate) (weak) (moderate) (moderate)

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

Table 4
BEEd Students' Performance in Undergraduate Courses (N = 31)

Courses	Rating	sd	Verbal Description
General Education Subjects	90.16	2.72	Very Good
Professional Education Subjects	92.32	2.21	Very Good
Average	91.24	2.30	Very Good

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	99% - 100%	Exceptional
	96% - 98%	Excellent
	93% - 95%	Superior
	90% - 92%	Very Good
	87% - 89%	Good
	84% - 86%	Above Average
	81% - 83%	Average
	78% - 80%	Below Average
	75% - 77%	Passing

Table 5
BEEd Students' Performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (N = 31)

Courses	Rating	sd	Verbal Description
General Education Subjects	80.16	5.21	Below Average
Professional Education Subjects	80.12	3.89	Below Average
Average	80.14	2.93	Below Average

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	99% - 100%	Exceptional
	96% - 98%	Excellent
	93% - 95%	Superior
	90% - 92%	Very Good
	87% - 89%	Good
	84% - 86%	Above Average
	81% - 83%	Average
	78% - 80%	Below Average
	75% - 77%	Passing

Table 6
*Relationship between BEd Students' Performance in Their Undergraduate Courses
 and Their Licensure Examination for Teachers (N = 31)*

Undergraduate Courses	Licensure Examination for Teachers			
	General Subjects	Ed. Professional Subjects	Ed. Average	
General Ed. Subjects	0.077 (very weak)	-0.006 (very weak)	0.043 (very weak)	
Professional Ed Subjects	0.304 (moderate)	0.425 (moderate)	0.384 (moderate)	
Average	0.250 (weak)	0.282 (weak)	0.282 (weak)	

Legend: Value of r Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)

Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

DISCUSSION

Shown in Table 1 is the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' performance in their undergraduate courses. It can be noticed that the BSEd students overall academic performance in their undergraduate courses is "Very Good" as reflected in its average rating of 91.19%.

The study revealed that the teacher education graduates under the Bachelor of Secondary Education program has a "Superior" academic performance in their major subjects and gained "Very good" and "Good" academic performances in their professional and general education subjects as indicated in the mean ratings of 92.7%, 91.45% and 89.39% respectively. The data also disclose that these students have "Very Good" academic performance in their undergraduate subjects as indicated in the composite mean rating of 91.9%. The result implies that the BSEd graduates have strong foundation in their professional general and specialized education subjects which marked as excellent preparations for the Licensure Examination for Teachers. Apra and Arcilla (2018) stressed that students' undergraduate courses can contribute to their performances in the LET. Faltado (2014) also emphasized the same when he mentioned that curriculum and instruction must be effectively delivered as this contributes to students' performance in the licensure examination for teachers

Presented in Table 2 are the data on the Bachelor of Secondary Education Students' Performance in the Licensure Examination for teachers. The result reflects that their overall performance rating in the LET is on the "Average" with a mean rating of 81.17. It can be gleaned from the data that they obtained "Average" ratings in their General education and Professional education subjects and "Below Average" in their major

subjects. The results suggest that while students possess a foundational understanding of general and professional education concepts, they struggle to demonstrate in-depth knowledge in their specialized areas.

Moreover, the performance in major subjects is particularly concerning as these areas are directly related to the specific teaching fields in which graduates will eventually work. A below-average performance indicates potential gaps in content mastery, which could adversely affect their ability to deliver quality education in their respective specializations once they enter the teaching profession. The results imply that teacher education institutions must design their instructional delivery which will consider the alignment between what is taught in their major courses and what is tested on the licensure examination to yield better outcomes.

Table 3 depicts the results on the relationship between BSEd Students' Academic Performance in their Undergraduate Courses and their ratings in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. For the BSEd program, strong correlation was revealed on their GPA and LET performance in the General Education subjects ($r=0.643$, $p<.05$). Moreover, weak to very weak correlation was also observed along BSEd students' academic performance and their performance in the LET in their Professional subjects ($r= 0.163$, $p<.05$) and their field of specialization, ($r=-0.030$, $p<.05$) respectively.

As a whole, the result showed "Moderate" correlation between the graduates GPA and LET performance ($r=0.346$, $p<.05$). Moreover, the study further indicated that for the BSEd program, a strong correlation was revealed on their GPA and LET performance in the General Education subjects ($r=0.643$, $p<.05$) and a weak to very weak correlation were also observed along BSEd students' academic performance and their performance in the LET in their Professional Education subjects ($r= 0.163$, $p<.05$) and their field of specialization, ($r=-0.030$, $p<.05$) respectively. The result is parallel to the findings of Paco and Allaga (2013) when they revealed that a moderate correlation exists between their graduates' LET performance and their general education subjects and a weak correlation was also found between teacher education students' academic performance and their LET results in both professional education and specialization subjects. This is confirmed in the study of Chan-Rabanal (2016), when she stressed that students' academic achievement is significantly related to LET performance.

In general, the result of the study showed "Moderate" correlation between the BSEd graduates GPA and LET performance ($r=0.346$, $p<.05$). This implies that students who obtained good grades in their General Education subjects in college got high ratings in the LET. On another note, it can also be gleaned from the results that their academic performance in Professional and specialization subjects in college only has a little impact in their LET ratings on the mentioned areas. The result is in opposition to the findings of Pachejo and Allagra as cited in the works of Amanonce and Maramag (2020), when they disclosed that there is a strong and significant correlation between teachers' grades in college and their LET performance.

Table 4 showed the data on Bachelor of Elementary Education students' performance in undergraduate courses. The result reflects that the Bachelor of

Elementary Education students' academic performance in their undergraduate subjects specifically General Education and Professional Education subjects showed a generally "Very Good" rating as indicated in their composite means of 90.16 and 92.24 respectively. These results suggest that the curriculum and instruction in these subjects are focused on equipping students with the needed competencies required for teaching. The students' remarkable performance in General Education and professional education subjects reflect that the students have gained broad understanding of various fields and are capable of integrating their knowledge across all areas, thus shaping them in becoming well rounded educators.

Shown in table 5 is the result of Bachelor of Elementary Education students' performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. The data infer that BEEEd students' performance in the LET is "below average" as reflected in the average rating of 80.14. It can be recalled in the data presented in table 4 that the BEEEd students showed Very good performances in both their professional and General education subjects but got below average rating in the LET as reflected in table 5. The result contradicts the findings revealed by Chan-Rabanal,(2016) in her study titled 'Academic Achievement and LET performance of BEEEd graduates in University of Northern Philippines when she unveiled that BEEEd students' academic performance is significantly related to their LET performance. The findings of the study indicate that there is a need for a multi-faceted approach to improving teacher education program, specially the Bachelor of Elementary education. It suggests the importance of revisiting the curriculum, enhanced faculty development, and a reevaluation of the admission processes which may include qualifying exams to be given to aspiring pre-service teachers to ensure that they are well-prepared to pass the licensure examination and excel in their future teaching endeavors.

Table 6 presents the relationship between BEEEd Students' Performance in their undergraduate courses and their Licensure Examination for teachers' results. The study discovered that the BEEEd students' performance in their undergraduate courses and their LET performance results in the Professional Education and General Education subjects showed "Moderate" and "Very Weak" relationships. These results imply that FUCE BEEEd students' academic performance in their professional and general education subjects are not strong predictors of their performance in the LET. The result negates the findings of Esmeralda and Perez-Espinosa (2015), and Amonce and Marawan (2020), when they disclosed that Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates' academic performance is a significant predictor in the Licensure Examination for Teachers as it was found in their study that a significant relationship between the students' LET performance and the academic achievement of students exists. The same was also claimed by Hena, et al. (2014), Quiambao, et al. (2015), and Ferrer and Ferrer (2015) when they stated that graduates grade point average has a high and positive correlation to LET performance.

Conclusions

The overall performance rating of the Bachelor of Secondary Education students in the Licensure Examination for Teachers is on the Average. Specifically, they obtained

Average ratings in their General Education and Professional Education subjects but Below Average in their Major Subjects. In like manner, the Bachelor of Elementary Education students showed below average in their performance rating in the LET.

There is a strong correlation on the GPA and LET performance in the General Education subjects for the Bachelor of Secondary Education program of the FUCE. However, there is a weak to very weak correlation of Bachelor of Secondary Education students' academic preparation and LET performance in their Professional subjects and their field of specialization. It should be noted

also that a moderate relationship exists between BEEd students' academic performance in their professional education subjects taken during their pre-service education and their LET results. Further, there is a very weak relationship between the academic performance and their general education subjects to their LET results.

Recommendations

To do a thorough revisit of the curriculum content and syllabi preparation process especially on the Professional Education subjects making content more aligned to PRC's competencies tested.

To substantiate and strengthen the efforts of the FUCE in the webinars and virtual workshops conducted, more capacity building activities among faculty especially those handling professional education subjects must be put in place to keep them more updated with the content and appropriate pedagogies in response to the call of the time.

To design mechanisms where students of the College of Education taking major subjects including the General Education subjects handled by faculty from the College of Arts and Sciences will not be merged with students from other colleges, hence making teaching and learning more developmentally appropriate to prospective teachers.

To strongly advise graduating students to enroll in a private review classes to better prepare them for the LET.

To improve the facilities and other resources of the college specifically by putting up an Educational Technology Laboratory by AY 2023-2024 in its desire to improve the LET performance of its graduates.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethics is highly observed during the conduct of the study, especially that the researchers are gathering the pre-service student teachers' academic performance and their LET results. A letter of request asking them the permission to access their grades in the professional education, general education and major subjects were sent to them as well as the letter asking the favour to submit to researchers a copy of their LET results. The gathered data were safeguarded with highest privacy and the anonymity of the names and identity of the respondents are kept.

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